

Validation of Aquacrop Model for various deficit irrigation schedules in Maize hybrid

A Bharathi*, T. Ragavan¹ and V. Geethalakshmi¹

*Assistant Professor, Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education, Virudhunagar

¹Professor, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore

Abstract

Field experiments were conducted at Agricultural College and Research Institute, TNAU, Madurai during summer 2017 and 2018 with different deficit irrigation treatments. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design, and replicated thrice under sandy clay loam soil. Experiments consisted of eleven treatments through drip system based on PE and ET_c approach viz., regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) at 80 and 60 percent (T_2 to T_5), alternate deficit irrigations (ADI) at 80 and 60 per cent (T_6 and T_7), critical stage-based deficits (T_8 to T_{11}) and conventional drip irrigation (CDI) at IW/CPE of 0.75 (T_1) for comparison. The test crop of CO(M)H-6, maize hybrid was used. Aquacrop model simulated and observed grain and biomass yield with water use efficiency (WUE). The validation efficiency of Aquacrop was tested by the statistical measures such as root mean square error (RMSE), normalised mean square error (NRMSE), Bias (BIAS), coefficient of determination (R^2) and index of agreement (D).

Keywords: Deficit irrigation, Aquacrop model, validation, statistical measures

INTRODUCTION

Irrigated agriculture is continuously being the major fresh water exploiting sector at global level. Water being a critical input, has received the attention of researchers and policy makers all over the world leading to development of different approaches to use the scarce water very judiciously. Of the approaches, the most recent advanced irrigation technology is deficit irrigation. It means irrigation scheduling in terms of changing quantities of irrigation water to be applied as well as changing frequency of intervals along with other agronomic management practices (Bharathi, 2020).

The crop simulation models are very powerful tools to understand the behavior of crop with response to water applied under different climatic conditions (Farahani *et al.*, 2009, Bharathi *et al.*, 2018). AquaCrop is the water driven model developed by Land

and Water Division of FAO to simulate yield response of several herbaceous crops to water. It is designed to balance simplicity, accuracy and robustness, and is particularly suited to address conditions where water is a key limiting factor in crop production. AquaCrop is a companion tool for a wide range of users and applications including yield prediction under climate change scenarios (Steduto *et al.*, 2009).

Yawson *et al.* (2010) simulated AquaCrop model for maize water productivity under rainfed condition and results showed that a coefficient of determination ($R = 0.81$) between farmers' yield and AquaCrop simulated yield. He concluded that AquaCrop has the ability to simulate the water productivity of crops with considerable accuracy under rainfed conditions in a tropical humid climate. Kipkorir *et al.* (2010) studied the application of AquaCrop model for prediction of maize yields in western Kenya. AquaCrop model was used to simulate yield with observed daily weather inputs and in response to selected historic rainfall data. Results indicated that yield predictions issued later in the growing season were more accurate than predictions issued earlier because they incorporated more close-to-actual weather conditions. They concluded that application of AquaCrop model would be useful for accurate yield estimates several months before harvest for strategic planning. Hsiao *et al.* (2009) investigated the AquaCrop model to simulate yield response to water for Maize. AquaCrop simulated the final above ground biomass within 10 per cent of the measured value and also the grain yield. The simulated results were within 5 per cent of the measured value for biomass as well as for grain yield. With this background the current research was done with various deficit irrigation schedules for Maize hybrid. Aquacrop model simulated and observed grain and biomass yield with water use efficiency (WUE) are furnished under.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field Experiment

Field experiment was conducted at Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai, to study the effect of varying deficit irrigation regimes in maize under drip irrigation system during summer, 2017. The experimental soil was texturally classified as sandy clay having 25.2 per cent field capacity, 12.5 per cent permanent wilting point and has $1.36 \text{ (g cc}^{-1}\text{)}$ bulk density. Soil has pH value of 7.95, organic carbon content of 0.36 per cent and EC of 1.55 dsm^{-1} . The available status of nitrogen in the soil was low (264 kg ha^{-1}), with medium phosphorus (18.5 kg ha^{-1}) and high in potassium (378 kg ha^{-1}). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design and the treatments were replicated thrice. Treatments comprised of seven irrigation levels through drip (Table 1). Drip irrigation

system was operated once in three days and irrigation was applied as per the treatments based on PE and ET_c levels.

Table 1. Treatment details

T ₁ – Conventional Irrigation at IW/CPE of 0.75
T ₂ – Irrigation at 80 % PE
T ₃ – Irrigation at 80 % ET _c
T ₄ – Irrigation at 60 % PE
T ₅ – Irrigation at 60 % ET _c
T ₆ – 80 and 60% PE as ADI [ADI – Alternate Deficit Irrigation]
T ₇ – 80 and 60% ET _c as ADI

The experimental field was thoroughly ploughed. Beds were formed in the dimensions of 120 cm width, 30 cm furrow and 15 cm height. Buffer channels were formed to control the lateral seepage of water from one plot to another. The plot size was 7.2 × 4.5 m, accommodating six rows of crop. Maize hybrid COHM-6, was used for the experimental study. Seeds were hand-dibbled at the rate of one per hole. Paired row spacing of 120 + 30 × 60 cm was followed. Sowing irrigation was uniformly given to all treatments.

Water requirement (litres per day or Lpd) or ET_c = CPE × K_p × K_c × W_p × S,

$$PE = CPE \times K_p$$

Where, ET_c = crop evapotranspiration,

CPE = cumulative pan evaporation (mm),

K_p = pan factor (0.8)

K_c = crop coefficient,

W_p = wetting area percentage (80%) (Veeraputhiran, 2000),

S = Crop spacing (0.60 × 0.25 m for maize).

Irrigation water was pumped from the water source and conveyed to the main line of 63-mm outer diameter (OD) polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipes after filtering through sand filter. In the main line, venturi was installed for fertigation. From the main, sub-mains of 40 mm OD PVC pipes were drawn, and from the sub-main, laterals of 12-mm low linear density polyethylene (LLDPE) pipes were installed at an interval of 1.2 m. Each lateral was provided with individual tap control for imposing respective irrigation schedules. Along the laterals, inline drippers with a discharge capacity of 4 L hr⁻¹ were spaced at 0.4 m. Single lateral was used for a paired row of maize. Sub-mains and laterals were closed at the end with end cap. After installation, trial run was conducted to assess mean dripper discharge and uniformity coefficient. This was taken into account while fixing the irrigation water application time.

During the irrigation period an average of 90–95% uniformity was observed. The recommended dose of fertilizer was applied as N: P₂O₅:K₂O @ 250:75:75 kg ha⁻¹. All the package of practices was carried out as per recommendation of CPG (2012).

All the relevant biometric observations on growth parameters were recorded at periodic interval of the crop growth stages *viz.*, 30, 60 DAS and at harvest stage. The yield and yield attributes of maize were recorded as per the procedure. Data of each character collected were statistically analyzed using standard procedure of variance analysis.

Aquacrop model simulation

Elaborating irrigation schedules and optimizing the water use merely on the basis of field research is expensive and time consuming. To optimize the irrigation schedule, it is advised to use simulation models as the decision can be made in short time. Several models are available to simulate yield response to water and Aquacrop is one of the important models developed by Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO).

Input requirement for setting up Aquacrop

Aquacrop model uses a relatively small number of explicit parameters and largely intuitive input variables, either widely used or requiring simple methods for their determination. Input consists of weather data, crop and soil characteristics, and management practices that define the environment in which the crop is grown.

1. Climate data

Aquacrop model requires minimum (T_a) and maximum (T_x) air temperature, reference evapotranspiration (ET₀) as a measure of the evaporative demand of the atmosphere, and rainfall on daily basis. Additionally, the mean annual CO₂ concentration has to be known. Historical line series of mean annual atmospheric CO₂ concentrations measured at Mauna Loa Observatory in Hawaii, as well as the expected concentrations for the near future are provided in Aquacrop model.

2. Crop characteristics

Aquacrop uses minimum number of crop parameters that describe the plant physiological and growth characteristics. It had been calibrated with crop parameters for major agriculture crops, and generic values are available in the model. However, distinction is made between conservative, cultivar-specific and less conservative parameters in Aquacrop. The conservative crop parameters do not change with time, management practices, or geographical locations. They were calibrated with data of crop grown under non-limiting fertilizer and water supply situations and remain applicable for stress conditions using stress response functions. Conservative parameters require no adjustment to the local conditions and can be used as such

in the Aquacrop simulation process. Cultivar specific or less- conservative crop parameters are affected by field management, conditions of the soil profile or the weather parameters. These parameters might require an adjustment during model calibration process to account for local varieties and local environmental conditions.

3. Soil characteristics

In Aquacrop model, the soil profile was partitioned to five different layers of variable depths to account for the altering physical characteristics, *viz.*, soil texture, hydraulic conductivity at saturation (Ksat), drainage coefficient, soil water content at saturation (SAT), field capacity (FC) and at permanent wilting point (PWP). The user can import the soil texture data of the experimental site with the help of pedo-transfer functions. Moreover, the existence of any impervious layer within or below the root zone needs to be specified during the model calibration process. This information will be used by the water budgeting module of Aquacrop to estimate the soil water content in the crop root zone leading to estimation of crop growth and yield.

4. Management practices

The options for management practices to stimulate the Aquacrop model are divided into two categories *viz.* field and irrigation management practices. Under field management practices, the choice of soil fertility levels, and practices that affect the soil water balance such as mulching to reduce soil evaporation, soil bunds to store water on the field, and tillage practices such as ridges or contours that reduce surface runoff were considered. Further, the four fertility levels such as non-limiting, near optimal, moderate and poor were considered in Aquacrop which affects the WP, rate of canopy growth, maximum canopy cover and the crop senescence Whereas, under irrigation management practices the Aquacrop model has the options for the rainfed and irrigated conditions. Further, under irrigated condition, user can select the application methods (*i.e* sprinkler, drip or surface methods), the fraction of wetted surface and specify the irrigation quantity and the timing for each irrigation event. There are also options to assess the net irrigation requirement and to generate irrigation schedules based on specified time and depth criteria. Since the criteria might change during the growing season, the model provides the means to test deficit irrigation strategies by applying chosen amounts of water at various stages of crop development.

Validation of Aquacrop model for Maize

Aquacrop model was validated using the field data from the experiments carried out at Agricultural College and Research Institute (AC & RI), Madurai.

1. Climate data

The daily weather data on sunshine hours (hrs), maximum and minimum air temperatures (°C), rainfall (mm), windspeed (m/s) and relative humidity (%) were collected from the meteorological observatory at AC&RI, Madurai.

2. Crop data

The crop components including initial canopy, canopy development, rooting depth, flowering and yield formation were recorded and used in Aquacrop model.

3. Soil data

The model required full dataset of a given soil texture viz., wilting point, field capacity, bulk density, hydraulic conductivity, saturation, total available water (TAW), fertility status and initial soil water content. These required soil parameters were estimated by analysing the soil of the experimental field.

4. Irrigation application

Experimental plots were prepared according to various deficit irrigation schedules. Irrigation was given in drip system once in 3 days.

Statistical indexes used for model validation

1. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

$$\text{RMSE (Root Mean Square Error)} = \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^n (S_i - O_i)^2}{n} \right]$$

Where S_i and O_i refer to the simulated and observed values for the studied variables, respectively. E.g. grain yield and total biomass and n is the mean of the observed variables. Normalized RMSE (RMSE_n) gives a measure (%) of relative difference of simulated verses observed data. The simulation is considered excellent with a normalized RMSE less than 10 per cent, good if the normalized RMSE is greater than 10 and less than 20 per cent, fair if the normalized RMSE is greater than 20 per cent and less than 30 per cent and poor, if the normalized RMSE is greater than 30 per cent (Loague and Green 1991). The RMSE_n was calculated following Equation.

$$\text{NRMSE (Normalized Root Mean Square Error)} = \left[\frac{\text{RMSE} \times 100}{\bar{O}} \right]$$

2. BIAS

BIAS was calculated as

$$\text{Bias} = n^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - O_i)$$

Where S_i : Simulated yield, O_i : Observed yield, n : Number of observations. BIAS measures the average tendency of simulated data to be larger or smaller than the observed counterparts. BIAS values with small magnitude are preferred. Positive values indicate model overestimation bias and negative values indicate underestimation model bias (Gupta and Nagar, 1999).

3. Coefficient of determination (R^2)

Coefficient of determination was calculated as follow, the coefficient of determination r^2 is defined as the squared value of the coefficient of correlation according to Bravais-Pearson. It is calculated as:

$$r^2 = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})(P_i - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2}} \right)^2$$

Where, O observed and S simulated values. R^2 can also be expressed as the squared ratio between the covariance and the multiplied standard deviations of the observed and simulated values. Therefore it estimates the combined dispersion against the single dispersion of the observed and simulated series. The range of r^2 lies between 0 and 1 which describes how much of the observed dispersion is explained by the simulated.

4. Index of agreement (d)

The index of agreement d was proposed by Willmot (1981) to overcome the insensitivity of E and r^2 to differences in the observed and simulated means and variances (Legates and McCabe, 1999). The index of agreement represents the ratio of the mean square error and the potential error (Willmot, 1984) and is defined as

$$d = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (|P_i - \bar{O}| + |O_i - \bar{O}|)^2}$$

Where, n is the number of observations, S_i is simulated and O_i is observed values.

According to the D-statistic, the closer the index value is to one, the better the agreement between the two variables that are being compared and vice versa.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Aquacrop model simulated and observed grain and biomass yield with water use efficiency (WUE) are furnished in Table 2. The results revealed that model simulated grain and biomass yield closely matched with the observed grain and biomass yield under all the irrigation treatments. Similarly model simulated WUE had good match with observed WUE. Aquacrop simulation revealed that maize productivity was found higher in IW/CPE based irrigation treatment compared to the various deficit irrigation schedules.

Table 2. Simulated and observed grain and biomass yield with water use efficiency (Summer, 2017)

Treatments	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		Biomass yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		WUE (kg ha mm ⁻¹)	
	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated	Observed	Simulated
T ₁	7571	7336	14283	13840	16.72	14.50
T ₂	7093	6922	13505	13179	15.67	14.36
T ₃	6755	6559	13034	12657	14.92	14.07
T ₄	6107	6033	12002	11857	13.49	13.91
T ₅	4290	4276	8618	8389	9.48	9.70
T ₆	6860	6527	13261	12617	15.15	14.14
T ₇	7233	7169	13672	13551	15.98	14.39
T ₈	5413	5642	10229	10661	11.96	13.01
T ₉	6166	5709	11638	10776	13.62	13.04
T ₁₀	5573	5318	10615	10129	12.31	12.91
T ₁₁	5952	5552	11266	10509	13.15	12.97

In order to employ the Aquacrop model for optimizing the irrigation in maize, the model parameters were adjusted based on the field experiment data and validated by comparing selected model outputs with the available observed data (Fig 1 -3). In the current study the Aquacrop model output on maize yield, biomass and water use efficiency (WUE) were validated by comparing with observed data.

Fig 1. Comparison between the simulated and observed grain yield (kg ha⁻¹) of Summer, 2017

Fig 2. Comparison between the simulated and observed biomass yield (kg ha⁻¹) of Summer, 2017

Fig 3. Comparison between the simulated and observed WUE (kg ha mm⁻¹) of Summer, 2017

The validation efficiency has been tested by the statistical measures such as BIAS Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Normalized RMSE (NRMSE), coefficient of determination (R²) and Index of agreement (d) and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison between observed and simulated values of grain yield, biomass and WUE (Summer, 2017)

Statistical Index	Grain Yield	Biomass	WUE
RMSE	260 kg ha ⁻¹	494 kg ha ⁻¹	1.08 kg ha mm ⁻¹
NRMSE	4.14%	4.12 %	7.82%
BIAS	-128 kg ha ⁻¹	-340 kg ha ⁻¹	-0.55 kg ha mm ⁻¹
R²	0.93	0.91	0.83
D	0.9	0.9	0.8

Less BIAS values of -128, -340 kg ha⁻¹ and -0.55 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹ and RMSE of 260, 494 kg ha⁻¹ and 1.08 kg ha⁻¹ mm⁻¹ for grain, biomass yield and WUE indicated that the Aquacrop model performance was acceptable in simulating grain, biomass yield and WUE. NRMSE values for grain, biomass yield and WUE were 4.14, 4.12 and 7.82 per cent which indicates model simulation is excellent as the NRMSE is < ±10 per cent and NRMSE was 7.82 per cent for WUE which indicates model is good (Loague and Green 1991). The R² value for grain yield, biomass and WUE was more than 0.9 to 0.8 indicating high degree of co linearity between simulated and measured data as opined by Bitri *et al.* (2014) and Sema Kale (2016). High D value (0.9 and 0.8) for grain yield, biomass and WUE indicating very high predictability of the model (Bitri *et al.*, 2014).

The R² values of 0.93, 0.91 and 0.83 respectively of grain yield, biomass and WUE through model statistics indicated that there was good agreement between observed and model simulated data. RMSE values for grain yield and biomass were found to be 260 and 494 kg ha⁻¹

indicating good match between simulated and observed values. WUE was also found to have lower RMSE of $1.08 \text{ kg ha mm}^{-1}$.

From the model simulation, based on NRMSE, it was found that the performance of model was categorised as excellent (<10 %) in predicting the maize grain yield (with a deviation of 4.14 %) and biomass (with a deviation of 4.12 %) and WUE (with a deviation of 7.82 %). The amount of deviation from the observed quantities was 128, 340 kg ha^{-1} and 0.55 kg ha mm^{-1} respectively of grain yield, biomass yield and WUE. Higher D value (0.8 to 0.9) showed good agreement between the simulated and observed values of all the three components

CONCLUSION

Good predictability of Aquacrop indicates its sufficient degree of simulation accuracy make it a valuable tool for estimating crop productivity under deficit irrigation as an on-farm water management strategies for improving the efficiency of water use in agriculture. So it is concluded that Aquacrop model can be used with a high degree of reliability in practical management, strategic planning of the use of water resources for irrigation.

REFERENCE

- Bharathi, A., T Ragavan, V Geethalakshmi, A Rathinasamy and R. Amutha. 2018. Influence of deficit irrigation schedules on nutrient uptake of maize hybrid under drip system. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 7(4):272-275
- Bharathi, A. 2020. Deficit Irrigation Strategy as an Adaptation Tool to Climate Change. In Book: *Climate Change and Agriculture – Volume 2*, AkiNik Publications, Delhi. Pp 1-26
- Bitri, M., Grazhdani, S., and Ahmeti, A. 2014. Validation of the AquaCrop model for full and deficit irrigated potato production in environmental condition of Korea Zone, South-eastern Albania.
- Crop production guide (CPG).2012.Published by DEE.TNAU offset press. Coimbatore.
- Farahani, H. J., Izzi, G., & Oweis, T. Y. (2009). Parameterization and Evaluation of the AquaCrop Model for Full and Deficit Irrigated Cotton All rights reserved. No part of this periodical may be reproduced or transmitted in any form or by any means, electronic or mechanical, including photocopying, recording, or any information storage and retrieval system, without permission in writing from the publisher. *Agronomy Journal*, 101, 469–476.
- Gupta, A. K., & Nagar, D. K. (2018). *Matrix variate distributions*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Hsaio, T.C., Heng, L., Steduto, P., Rojas-Lara, B., Raes, D and Fereres, E. 2009. AquaCrop - The FAO crop model to simulate yield response to water:III. Parameterization and testing for maize. *Agron.J.*, 101:448-459.

- Kipkorir, E.C., Mugalavai, E.M., and Bargerei, R.J. 2010. Application of AquaCrop model for within-season prediction maize yield. IN: Workshop of Capacity Development for Farm Management Strategies to Improve Crop-Water Productivity using AquaCrop.2010, Yogyakarta, Indonesi.,8-10:Dec.57-64.
- Loague, K., and Green, R. E. 1991. Statistical and graphical methods for evaluating solute transport models: overview and application. *Journal of contaminant hydrology.*,7(1-2): 51-73.
- Sema Kale, S. 2016. Assessment of AQUACROP model in the simulation of wheat growth under different water regimes. *Scientific Papers-Series A, Agronomy.*, 59: 308-314.
- Steduto, P., Hsiao, T. C., Raes, D., & Fereres, E. (2009). AquaCrop—The FAO crop model to simulate yield response to water: I. Concepts and underlying principles. *Agronomy Journal*, 101, 426–437.
- Veeraputhiran, R., & Chinnusamy, C. (2009). Soil moisture and water use studies under drip and furrow irrigation methods in hybrid cotton. *Journal of Cotton Research and Development*, 23, 74–79.
- Willmott, C. J. 1981. On the validation of models, *Physical Geography. Spatial statistic and models.*, 18.
- Willmott, C. J. 1984. On the evaluation of model performance in physical geography. In *Spatial statistics and models* (pp. 443-460). Springer Netherlands.
- Yawson, D.O., Sam-Amoah, L.K., Armah, F.A. 2010. AquaCrop simulation of rainfed maize water productivity in south-central Ghana. IN: Workshop of Capacity Development for Farm Management Strategies to Improve Crop-Water Productivity using AquaCrop.2010, Y Yogyakarta, Indonesi.,8-10:Dec.26-31.